

THE IMPORTANCE OF “MASNAVI-YI MANAVI” BY JALALIDDIN RUMI IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY PSYCHOLOGY

U.O. Fayzullayev

Lecturer, “Psychology” Department, Mamun University, Urganch city

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18175756>

Abstract. *After gaining independence, the attention paid to studying the heritage of our scholars, the importance of studying the great heritage in raising the spirituality of the younger generation, the life and work of Mevlana Jalaliddin Rumi and others will be discussed.*

Keywords: *independence, spiritual heritage, national, spiritual-enlightenment life, Sufism, philosophical-mystical views, education, masnavi. etc.*

Introduction

It is important to note from the very first years of independence; profound developments began to be felt in all spheres of our society. It is no secret to any of us that the revival of our national culture, historical monuments, national traditions, and values has been serving as a fundamental cornerstone for the prosperity of our present day.

At the same time, the era itself demands a deep understanding of national identity, the restoration, research, and promotion of our spiritual heritage, and the integration of the scientific and philosophical views of our great thinkers and Sufi scholars into the social and spiritual life of our people, using their invaluable moral and educational ideas to meet the spiritual and psychological needs of society. The integrated study of material and spiritual existence has long been regarded as one of the qualities inherent in our people’s mentality.

Certainly, after achieving independence, significant changes took place in the spiritual and educational world of our people. In particular, from the very first years of independence, special attention was paid to the development of views on moral and ethical values consistent with Eastern ethical principles. Considerable efforts were made to develop social views that serve the spiritual progress of society, such as patriotism, tolerance, humanism, nobility, duty, conscience, justice, and honesty.

It is well known that the concept of tolerance has various applications and forms, and personal tolerance is considered one of the most important human qualities. Taking this into account, it is especially timely to widely utilize the knowledge and findings obtained through psychological analysis of aspects related to personal tolerance found in the works of great scholars who emerged in the East, in order to foster tolerance in individuals.

In raising our youth to be healthy-minded and well-rounded individuals, as well as in the development of our society and the moral, educational, cultural, and ethical advancement of humanity as a whole, mutual tolerance is regarded as one of the most important factors.

During the years of independence, special attention was also given to carrying out a number of scientific research projects aimed at studying the spiritual heritage of our great scholars. In the vast land of the East, thousands of saints and thinkers who achieved perfection in intellect and knowledge gained fame. One such great figure is Mawlana Jalaliddin Rumi. Abdurahman Jami described this great personality as follows:

He is unique in the world of meaning;
The “Masnavi” is proof of his true essence.
What more can I say in praise of his noble qualities?
He has a book, yet he is not a prophet.

Mawlana Jalal al-Din Rumi, through his incomparable works, captivated both the East and the West. His works such as “Masnaviy Manavi,” “Fihi Ma Fihi” (What is within is within), “Seven Sermons,” and “Open the Eye of the Heart” are widely known among the people. Especially “Masnaviy Manavi” is a work that has been highly acclaimed by scholars all over the world. This masterpiece is rich in ideas that play an important role in the proper development of an individual’s psychological characteristics.

The factors in the work that encourage mutual tolerance are of great importance in shaping the personality of the younger generation on the basis of personal and psychological qualities aligned with the principles of tolerance. In one place, Rumi is described as: “The great Mawlana who calls to goodness the essence of souls, the secret of the lamp, glass, and lantern, the sun of religion and truth, the light of God for those before and after.” Alisher Navoi, meanwhile, acknowledges him as: “Mawlana Rumi - the singer of divine love, an imperceptible peak among the great,” and “the master of masters, the teacher of the secrets of truth, the diver in the ocean of those who have recognized God.”

The great Indian enlightenment poet Muhammad Iqbal describes him by saying: “For saving this world from despair and to acquaint humanity with joy and enthusiasm, another Rumi is needed.” Sayyid Nematullah Ibrahim glorifies him in the following lines:

If the heart is in love with Truth, where is its cry?
Where is a king of enlightenment like Mawlavi?

The Sufism scholar M. Istelami described Mawlana as follows: “He is sometimes compared to philosophers such as Kant, Spinoza and Hegel.

However, Mawlana Rumi resembles no one; he is a miraculous monument of the great Eastern intellect, in whom the development of Sufism, knowledge and wisdom, philosophy, poetry, and spirituality are united and manifested in their highest form. I. Haqqul, in turn, expresses the following view: “A person, who distances himself from Rumi falls into despair. A person who does not read Rumi becomes self-centered.”

In general, the studies carried out on the scholarly heritage of Jalaliddin Rumi can be divided into two groups. The first group consists of research devoted to the scholar’s personality, life, family, and close associates. The second group includes works focused on studying the thinker’s scholarly heritage, his philosophical and mystical views, and his Sufi ideas. However, it must be acknowledged that studies belonging to the first group are few in number, while those of the second group are quite numerous worldwide. In this context, it is appropriate to briefly touch upon Mawlana’s personality and life.

Jalaliddin Rumi was born in the village of Vakhsh near the city of Balkh, located in what is now northern Afghanistan and which at that time belonged to the Khwarazmshahs. The city of Balkh, where Muhammad Jalal al-Din matured, was one of the major centers of political, economic, spiritual, and cultural development of its era, and was also known by the names “Umm al-Bilad” (“Mother of Cities”) and “Qubbat al-Islam.”

Conclusion

Sources provide differing years regarding the date of birth of this great figure. The prominent Turkish Rumi scholar Mehmet Under, director of the Mawlana Museum established

near the mausoleum of Mawlana Jalal al-Din Rumi in the city of Konya, Turkey, notes in his work “Mawlana” that historian Will Durant suggested that Mawlana was born in 1201, while Maurice Barrès assumed his birth to be in 1203. Mehmet Under himself offers the following opinion: “In recent years, scholars who have conducted extensive research on this topic state that Mawlana was born well before 1207. That is, in his work “Fihi Ma Fihi” Mawlana refers to the siege of Samarkand by the Khwarazmshahs, suggesting: ‘We were in Samarkand; the Khwarazmshah was besieging Samarkand, mobilizing troops and fighting.’”

REFERENCES

1. Jalal al-Din Rumi. *Majalis al-Saba (Seven Sessions)*. Tashkent: 2018. P. 174.
2. Jalal al-Din Rumi. *Sayings (Wisdoms)*. Tashkent: 2008. P. 228.
3. Jorayev, N. *Theoretical Foundations of the Philosophy of History*. Tashkent: Manaviyat, 2008. P. 150.
4. *Islamic Encyclopedia*. Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2017. P. 390.
5. Mawlana Jalaliddin Rumi. *Methodological and bibliographic guide*. Compiled by U. Teshaboeva. Tashkent, 2007. P. 21.
6. *Fundamentals of Philosophy*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2005.